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To cite this article: Manuel Lara *et al* 2026 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3224** 052002

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Feedforward individual pitch control of wind turbines in the nominal region

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Abstract. To mitigate periodic loads on wind turbine blades, engineers employ individual pitch control (IPC) strategies. These systems implement individual commands for each blade, operating in conjunction with collective pitch control (CPC), which regulates the turbine rotational speed. Despite the efficacy of IPC methods in reducing blade fatigue in comparison with CPC alone, they substantially increase the pitch activity, which damage the actuators. This research addresses this critical trade-off by introducing a novel adaptive feedforward IPC strategy. This novel approach offers the crucial ability to adjust the IPC control effort, a feature challenging to implement in conventional systems and one which has been minimally explored in previous studies. The present paper analyses the balance between reducing fatigue and increasing control effort using a simulation of a 15 MW monopile wind turbine operating in the nominal region. The proposed balanced IPC achieves a similar percentage (15-20 %) compared to the CPC, both in terms of fatigue reduction and increase of control effort.

1. Introduction

The European Union considers the fight against climate change a priority, promoting substantial reductions in greenhouse gas emissions and encouraging similar initiatives at the global level. With electricity generation accounting for almost a third of global emissions, wind energy has established itself as an increasingly viable alternative due to its reduced environmental impact. However, increasing dimensions and capacity of wind turbines results in exposure to greater structural loads, particularly those arising from gravitational and aerodynamic forces. When such loads are not appropriately managed, they have the potential to compromise system performance and precipitate premature failure. Consequently, it is essential to analyse how these forces influence the efficiency and life of the turbine. From the viewpoint of a control system, the minimisation of such loads is crucial for extending the lifespan of wind turbines [1].

Modern wind turbines typically adopt a conventional design, characterised by a horizontal shaft with three blades. These devices are capable of variable speed operation in conjunction with a blade pitch adjustment system, which enables them to modify their performance according to wind speed through different modes of operation. The present study focuses exclusively on the nominal region, where the generator torque is kept fixed at its nominal value and the rotor speed regulation depends solely on the pitch system [1]. In this operating range, the control actions that directly influence structural life are those associated with blade movement, since strategies based on generator torque control—relevant in the sub-nominal region—do not intervene in the

Figure 1. (a) In-Plane (M_{xi}) and Out-of-Plane (M_{yi}) moments of blade i , which are referenced to the rotational coordinate system of this blade. (b) Tilt and yaw moments in the fixed coordinate system after applying the MBC transform to the Out-of-Plane moments.

dynamics under consideration. Therefore, the analysis of the impact of control on fatigue is approached from the perspective of pitch, which is the dominant control mechanism in this region.

To reduce fatigue loads on wind turbine blades, one option is the implementation of Individual Pitch Control (IPC) [2]. Conversely, the conventional approach to rotational speed control within the nominal region is based on Collective Pitch Control (CPC), in which all blades are adjusted to the same angle in order to regulate power output and counteract wind variations. However, there has been an increasing trend of modern turbines incorporating IPC systems. One of the main benefits of IPC is its ability to reduce wear on key turbine elements, such as the hub, tower and rotor blades, without significantly compromising power generation.

The aerodynamic forces exerted on the blades can be classified into in-plane loads, which are tangential to the rotor, and out-of-plane (OoP) loads, which are oriented perpendicular to its surface, as illustrated in Figure 1a [3]. These forces manifest at frequencies that are multiples of the turbine rotational speed, with the 1P component being the most relevant. Initially, these bending moments are measured using sensors installed on the blades; however, these measurements are influenced by the rotational coordinate system of each blade, where the bending moment OoP at the root of blade i is represented as M_{yi} for $i = 1, 2, 3$, as shown in Figure 1a. To overcome this challenge, multi-blade coordinate (MBC) transformation is widely applied in IPC research, converting these signals from a rotational system to a fixed reference system [4]. This conversion yields a fixed reference frame, generating two main components: the tilt moment M_{tilt} and the yaw moment M_{yaw} (see Figure 1b). The IPC strategy seeks to reduce these decoupled moments, although in practice some degree of coupling often persists. Some authors propose to include an azimuth offset in the reverse MBC transform to improve the decoupling [4].

One of the growing areas in the field of wind turbine control is the application of computational intelligence [5], with a particular focus on genetic algorithms (GAs), to enhance the efficiency of control systems. In earlier studies [3][6], various IPC approaches that had been optimised by GAs were analysed with the aim of minimising blade fatigue. However, the increase in actuator stress caused by IPC was not considered. This increase in pitch activity is a well-documented, albeit little studied, drawback of IPC [7] and underlines the importance of assessing the

trade-off between the reduction of structural loads and pitch actuator stress. Although the basic structure of the IPC based on MBC transformation is widely established, recent literature has explored advanced approaches that address this trade-off between load reduction and actuator effort using constraint techniques, robust control, or MPC. These include output-constrained methods [7], robust H_∞ schemes [8], and predictive controllers [9].

However, these approaches often involve greater computational complexity and more intrusive integration into the control architecture. The novelty of this work lies in reformulating the IPC into a feedforward scheme with adaptation using gain scheduling based on the average blade moment, also introducing an explicit adjustment parameter that allows direct modulation of the trade-off between load reduction and actuator activity. This formulation, which is low in complexity and can be integrated into existing controllers, offers a practical alternative to the advanced methods mentioned above. It is designed to reduce the 1P cyclic loads of the blades in the IEA 15 MW Reference Wind Turbine (RWT) model in the nominal region. A comparison is made between its performance and that of a conventional PI-based CPC derived from the Reference Open-Source Controller (ROSCO). The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the background on IPC, Section 3 describes the proposed methodology and its design, Section 4 presents a comparative analysis of the response of the proposed scheme, and finally, Section 5 provides the main conclusions.

2. Background on individual blade pitch control

This section discusses the basics of IPC, focusing on the reduction of 1P harmonic loads on the blades of three-bladed wind turbines. Initially, these moments are measured within the rotational coordinate system of each blade, where the OoP bending moment at the root of blade i is represented as M_{y_i} for $i = 1, 2, 3$, as shown in Figure 1a. The individual OoP bending moments of the rotational system are organised in a vector $\mathbf{M}(t) = [M_{y_1}(t) \ M_{y_2}(t) \ M_{y_3}(t)]^T$. To facilitate their control, these measurements are converted from this rotational system to a fixed reference system by means of the forward MBC transformation $\mathbf{T}_F(\boldsymbol{\psi})$, as described in (1). This conversion generates two main components in the fixed reference frame: the tilt moment $M_t(t)$ and the yaw moment $M_y(t)$, as shown in Figure 1b. In this context, $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ denotes the vector of azimuth angles of the blades, with each value representing the location of the blade in relation to the rotor. An azimuthal angle of zero indicates that the blade is in the upper vertical position. The corresponding transformation matrix $\mathbf{T}_F(\boldsymbol{\psi})$ is given in equation (2).

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_t(t) \\ M_y(t) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_F(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \mathbf{M}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{T}_F(\boldsymbol{\psi}) = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi_1) & \cos(\psi_2) & \cos(\psi_3) \\ \sin(\psi_1) & \sin(\psi_2) & \sin(\psi_3) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Once the tilt and yaw moments in the fixed reference frame have been determined, the controllers of the IPC strategy obtain the corresponding non-rotating pitch components $\beta_t(t)$ and $\beta_y(t)$. Subsequently, these signals are converted back to the rotational coordinate system, applying the reverse MBC transformation $\mathbf{T}_R(\boldsymbol{\psi})$, which allows the specific pitch angles to be calculated for each blade, as described in equations (3) and (4) for the 1P loads, considered the most relevant.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \beta_{IPC1}(t) \\ \beta_{IPC2}(t) \\ \beta_{IPC3}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_R(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \begin{bmatrix} \beta_t(t) \\ \beta_y(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2. Conventional IPC scheme based on MBC transformations.

$$\mathbf{T}_R(\boldsymbol{\psi}) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi_1) & \sin(\psi_1) \\ \cos(\psi_2) & \sin(\psi_2) \\ \cos(\psi_3) & \sin(\psi_3) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

As illustrated in the schematic in Figure 2, the IPC typically consists of: a) the forward MBC transformation to obtain the tilt and yaw moments in a fixed coordinate system from the OoP moments; b) control scheme, which generally employs two decentralised controllers $C_t(s)$ and $C_y(s)$ to minimise M_t and M_y , generating the signals β_t and β_y , respectively; and c) the reverse MBC transformation, which converts β_t and β_y back into three individual pitch signals β_{IPCi} in the rotational coordinate system. The internal control of the IPC can be approached as a multivariable system with two outputs and two inputs. A similar parallel scheme can be used for other harmonics such as 2P loads [10].

The IPC is combined with the CPC in the overall control scheme acting on the blade pitch angle and shown in Figure 3. Both control systems work together to generate the total pitch signals required for the operation of the pitch actuator of each blade. Since the turbine is assumed to operate in the nominal region, with a fixed output at its rated power, the generator torque T_g is maintained at its nominal value. The CPC has the function of regulating the rotor speed ω_b , counteracting variations in wind speed. Thanks to this integration, the system simultaneously manages to regulate the turbine power and reduce the structural loads affecting the blades.

3. Proposed methodology

3.1 Wind turbine simulation environment

The simulations are performed using a co-simulation framework integrating MATLAB/Simulink with OpenFAST [11]. The model used corresponds to the 15 MW IEA RWT reference wind turbine [12]. This turbine has a rated power of 15 MW, operates with a rotor speed of 7.56 rpm and reaches its maximum output when the wind speed is 10.59 m/s. The pitch control system is subject to a rotational speed restriction of 2 deg/s. All simulations are performed at operating points within the nominal region, where the load on the blades increases due to the increase in wind speed and bending moment fluctuations [13]. In this operating range, the rotor speed is regulated by a pitch controller, while the torque is kept fixed at its nominal value. A pre-configured Proportional-Integral (PI) controller with scheduled gain derived from the Reference OpenSource Controller

(ROSCO) is used [14]. Two types of wind profiles are used in this work: steady for design and turbulent for validation. Turbsim [15] is used to generate the turbulent profiles at different operating points. These profiles follow a Kaimal turbulence spectrum with a turbulence intensity of 10% at hub height. A wind shear profile with power law exponent 0.2 is also applied. The wind profiles are 1000 s and sampled at 200 Hz. A still-water condition is assumed because wave effects are not expected to significantly influence blade fatigue for monopile offshore wind turbines.

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3.2 Proposed feedforward IPC with gain-scheduling

In the conventional IPC scheme in Figure 2, the tilt and yaw moment references are zero. Assuming integral action in the controllers $C_t(s)$ and $C_y(s)$ and steady wind conditions without turbulence, for each wind speed, the system reaches stationary values of β_t and β_y . The present study proposes a feedforward IPC scheme with gain-scheduling adaptation, designed based on the obtaining of these stationary values for different wind speeds. The scheme is shown in Figure 4, where there is no forward MBC transform, only the reverse. As wind speed is more difficult to measure, it is proposed that the average OoP momentum of the blades, denoted by \bar{M} , should be used as the scheduling variable, since it is strongly correlated with wind speed and is not significantly affected by the IPC parameters, which mainly affect the deviation of the moments around this average value. After multiple simulations performed with a conventional IPC incorporating integral action for different wind speeds with a steady profile, the stationary average values of \bar{M} , β_t and β_y were

Figure 3. General CPC+IPC scheme in the nominal region.

Table 1. Stationary results for the proposed feedforward IPC design.

Wind speed (m/s)	\bar{M} (MN·m)	β_t (°)	β_y (°)
14	34.96	1.2032	-0.4927
16	28.69	1.3293	-0.6073
18	24.05	1.4553	-0.7334
20	20.34	1.5756	-0.8537
22	17.25	1.6902	-0.9855

obtained for each wind speed. They are collected in Table 1. Using these values, the adaptation block in Figure 4 is designed. The factor k is a tuning parameter, ranging from 0 and 1, that enables to consider the trade-off between the blade fatigue reduction and the increase in the pitch actuator effort in a straightforward manner. A value of $k=0$ results in the cancelation of the IPC, whereas a value of $k=1$ makes the proposed scheme highly analogous to the conventional IPC. Although the OoP moments of the blades are measured to calculate the average value for gain-scheduling, the proposed scheme is feedforward since it does not calculate the M_t and M_y moments, which are the controlled variables in the IPC based on the MBC transform. The gain scheduling map $(\beta_t, \beta_y)=f(\bar{M})$ is obtained by linear interpolation between the stationary points in Table 1, and the factor k acts as a direct scaling of these references. The implementation is carried out as a static block in Simulink, without additional dynamics, which allows the scheme to be replicated directly in any co-simulation with OpenFAST.

3.3 Limiting control signals in the feedforward IPC

Next, the CPC without IPC ($k=0$) is compared with the CPC plus IPC scheme proposed in Figure 4 with $k=1$. First, for the design stage, constant wind profiles are used; then the control schemes will be analysed using a turbulent wind profile, which provides more realistic results. For each case, the damage equivalent load (DEL) of the blades is calculated, which is the index commonly used to assess wind turbine loads. The DEL is calculated from time series data using cycle counting methods; MLife, a toolkit developed by NREL, has been used for post-processing. The control effort is also calculated using the normalised average travel (NAT) of the pitch actuator; the expression

Figure 4. Proposed feedforward IPC scheme with adaptation via gain-scheduling and with the tuning parameter k for adjusting the trade-off between blade load reduction and pitch actuator effort.

Table 2. Results of the CPC with feedforward IPC with $k=1$ and CPC without IPC ($k=0$).

Wind speed (m/s)	$k=1$			$k=0$		
	\bar{M} (MN·m)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	NAT(β_1) (%)	\bar{M} (MN·m)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	NAT(β_1) (%)
14	34.96	2.57	32.7	34.74	11.32	0.32
16	28.69	2.81	36.8	28.41	13.27	0.12
18	24.05	3.11	41.0	23.72	15.27	0.06
20	20.34	3.39	45.1	19.97	17.31	0.04
22	17.25	3.65	49.2	16.81	19.38	0.03

is given in (5), where $\dot{\beta}_{max}$ is the highest allowed rate of change in the pitch actuator. Table 2 shows the data obtained for a CPC control with the feedforward IPC ($k=1$) and the data obtained for the CPC control without any IPC ($k=0$). The table also shows the average values of the blade OoP moments achieved for each case.

$$\text{NAT}(\beta_1) = \frac{1}{t_{\text{sim}} - t_0} \int_{t_0}^{t_{\text{sim}}} \left| \frac{\dot{\beta}_1(t)}{\dot{\beta}_{\text{max}}} \right| dt \quad (5)$$

The proposed IPC achieves significant reductions in DEL(M_{y1}), between 20-24 %. However, these reductions are achieved at the cost of large increases in NAT(β_1), between 32-49 %, compared to the reference CPC. In a conventional IPC scheme with integral controllers, if the reference of both moments M_t and M_y is zero, β_t and β_y will always reach stationary values leading large values of the NAT [3][6], even if the integral gains are small in absolute value. However, in the proposed feedforward IPC, the signals β_t and β_y can be limited by multiplying both by the same factor k between 0 and 1. The smaller the factor k , the lower the NAT values are obtained, although at the cost of lower reductions in the DEL of the blades. By varying this factor, intermediate designs can be obtained between the reference CPC without IPC ($k=0$) and the total feedforward IPC ($k=1$). To test this idea, the same tests have been carried out with stationary wind profiles for values of $k = 0.25, 0.5$, and 0.75 . The values obtained are shown in Table 3. With the data of \bar{M} from tables 2

Table 3. Results of the CPC with feedforward IPC for the cases: $k=0.25, 0.5$, and 0.75 .

Wind speed (m/s)	$k=0.25$			$k=0.5$			$k=0.75$		
	\bar{M} (MN·m)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	NAT(β_1) (%)	\bar{M} (MN·m)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	NAT(β_1) (%)	\bar{M} (MN·m)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	NAT(β_1) (%)
14	34.78	8.77	8.2	34.83	6.24	16.4	34.89	3.83	24.6
16	28.46	10.25	9.2	28.53	7.26	18.4	28.61	4.41	27.6
18	23.78	11.79	10.3	23.86	8.33	20.5	23.95	5.01	30.7
20	20.04	13.36	11.3	20.13	9.43	22.5	20.23	5.66	33.8
22	16.90	14.95	12.3	17.00	10.53	24.6	17.12	6.26	36.9

and 3 for each value of k and the pitch values of Table 1, the gain-scheduling map for the calculation block of β_t and β_y in Figure 4 can be implemented.

4. Results

4.1 Analysis for turbulent wind profiles

This section analyses how the proposed feedforward IPC responds using more realistic turbulent wind profiles and how the k factor influences the DEL and NAT. Tests are performed for turbulent wind profiles with the characteristic commented in subsection 3.1 and different average wind speeds. Table 4 shows the average DEL and NAT values obtained for the different simulations for each k value and mean wind speed. The higher the average wind speed, the higher the DEL of the OoP moments of the blades. For $k=1$, an average DEL reduction of 23.7 % is achieved in comparison with the CPC ($k=0$), at the cost of an average increase of 36.5 % of the NAT. For $k=0.75$, the average DEL reduction is 22% with a 26.3% increase in NAT. For $k=0.5$, the average DEL reduction and NAT increase are similar: 16.2%. For $k=0.25$, the average DEL reduction is only 8.7% whilst the NAT increase is 6.5 %. Figure 5a shows the variation of DEL versus NAT with varying k for different average wind speeds. The DEL-NAT trade-off is evident in the various fronts, with an increase in wind speed resulting in a wider range of variation for both indices. For a given value of k , the DEL-NAT trade-off as a function of wind speed is almost linear specifically for winds greater than 14 m/s. Figure 5b shows the variation of DEL (top) and NAT (bottom) with respect to the factor k . The variation of the NAT of the blades for the same wind and for $k > 0.2$ is linear, but not that of the DEL of the blades. This does not decrease significantly for values of $k > 0.75$, but there is an appreciable increase in the NAT. Therefore, it does not seem to be justified to use values of k greater than 0.75; nor values lower than 0.25, as they reduce the DEL very little. A good compromise value might be $k=0.5$, where the percentage reduction in DEL is equal to the increase in NAT.

4.2 Time response for turbulent wind

Next, four control schemes were compared for a turbulent wind profile with a mean wind speed of 20 m/s. These schemes are the reference CPC ($k=0$), the full IPC ($k=1$), the balanced IPC with $k=0.5$, as the best compromise, and a conventional IPC with two integral controllers (IPC_I). Table 5 shows the results of a 1000-s simulation, including the DEL(M_{y1}), the NAT(β_1), the mean generated power and its standard deviation (STD). The mean and standard deviation of the power

Table 4. DEL and NAT values for different turbulent wind profiles and k values.

Wind speed (m/s)	DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)					NAT(β_1) (%)				
	$k=0$	$k=0.25$	$k=0.5$	$k=0.75$	$k=1$	$k=0$	$k=0.25$	$k=0.5$	$k=0.75$	$k=1$
14	23.5	21.8	20.4	19.1	18.5	6.2	9.9	17.2	25.1	33.2
16	24.1	22.1	20.4	19.0	18.9	5.0	10.2	18.9	27.9	37.0
18	26.5	24.1	22.0	20.5	20.3	4.4	11.0	20.9	31.1	41.3
20	29.6	26.8	24.3	22.5	22.2	4.1	11.8	22.8	34.0	45.3
22	31.3	28.3	25.7	23.7	22.6	3.7	12.7	24.8	37.0	49.2

Figure 5. (a) Variation of DEL in relation to NAT when varying the factor k ; (b) Variation of DEL (top) and NAT (bottom) with respect to k factor.

Table 5. Performance indices for a turbulent wind profile with mean wind speed of 20 m/s.

Control	IPC ($k=1$)	IPC ($k=0.5$)	IPC ($k=0$)	IPC _i
DEL(M_{y1}) (MN·m)	23.49	26.01	31.16	23.41
NAT(β_1) (%)	45.67	23.22	4.31	47.47
$P_g/P_{g,rated}$ (%)	99.98	99.97	99.97	99.98
STD($P_g/P_{g,rated}$) (%)	5.43	5.42	5.39	5.42

are expressed as percentages relative to the nominal power. These normalised values are the same for the generator rotational speed ω_g . The full IPC reduces the DEL by 24.6 % in comparison with the CPC ($k=0$); however, an increase in the NAT from 4.3 % to 45.7 % (an increase of 41.4 %) has been observed. The balanced IPC achieves a 16.5 % reduction in the DEL with only a 18.9 % increase in the NAT. The conventional IPC (IPC_i) reduces the DEL by 24.9 %, which is slightly greater than the proposed full IPC, with an increase of 43.2% in the NAT. Furthermore, the proposed IPCs do not have impact on the CPC loop: the mean values and standard deviations of P_g are practically identical for all cases. Figure 6 illustrates the time responses of the simulation, with a window of only 100 seconds (from 700 to 800 s) selected for clarity. Figure 6, to the left, shows the following variables related to the rotational frame: the wind speed, the generated power, the bending OoP moment of blade 1 and the pitch signal of blade 1. The IPCs show reductions in blade 1 momentum without affecting the generated power. As expected, this is accompanied by an increase in pitch activity, and in the IPC case with $k=0.5$ the increase in these oscillations is smaller than in the IPC with $k=1$ and IPC_i. Figure 6, to the right, shows the time responses of the following variables in the fixed coordinate frame: tilt moment, yaw moment, tilt pitch, and yaw pitch. The pitch signals within the IPC are much smoother than those of the conventional IPC. This is consistent with the

lower NAT values obtained by the proposed IPCs. The larger the k value, the greater the mean absolute value of the tilt and yaw pitch signals. The tilt and yaw moments shows similar responses but are vertically shifted; the larger the k value, the closer their mean value approaches zero.

5. Conclusions

This paper proposes an adaptive feedforward IPC scheme for wind turbines that allows to consider in a very simple way the trade-off between the reduction of blade fatigue and the increase of the control effort of the pitch actuators. It has been found that there is a practically linear relationship of the proposed tuning factor k and the increase of NAT. For values of $k=0.5$, a compromise is achieved in which the reduction in % of the DEL of the OoP moments of the blades with respect to the CPC and the increase in % in NAT are similar.

The analysis carried out in the nominal region confirms that the proposed scheme is capable of significantly reducing OoP loads without affecting the performance of the speed loop, which is already stabilised by the ROSCO controller. In addition, the feedforward formulation avoids the high steady-state values of the pitch signals that often appear in schemes with integral action, which helps to limit the stress on the actuators. However, the study has some limitations inherent to its scope. The analysis was performed under standard turbulent conditions in order to isolate the effect of the parameter k , and does not include a formal stability or robustness study. The evaluation of the scheme's behaviour in the face of more severe disturbances—such as wake interactions, model uncertainties, or pronounced non-linearities of the actuators—is a necessary line of future work to assess its performance in more demanding scenarios. Likewise, future work will

Figure 6. (left) Time responses of wind speed, generated power, OoP moment of blade 1, and pitch of blade 1; (right) Time responses of tilt moment, yaw moment, tilt pitch, and yaw pitch.

focus on integrating the proposed approach with closed controllers without integral action in the IPC block, with the aim of expanding its applicability and improving its rejection capacity in the face of unmodelled disturbances.

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities under granted project PID2023-149181OB-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, EU.

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